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WORK ORGANISATION AND WORKFORCE VULNERABILITY TO NON- EMPLOYMENT:

evidence from OECD's survey on adult
skills (PIAAC)

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Abstract

This paper examines the relationship between the different forms of work organisation in workplaces and the vulnerability of the workforce to non-employment within countries taking part in the Programme for the Assessment of Adults Competencies (PIAAC) – a cross-country survey carried out by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). It uses hierarchical cluster analysis to define five forms of work organisation based on the description given by employees of the tasks they perform. Then multilevel logistic regression is used to evaluate their impact on vulnerability to non-employment. The latter is defined as being currently non-employed while having been employed at some point during the last twelve months previous the PIAAC survey. The results show indeed a significant impact of work organisation on vulnerability to non-employment after controlling for relevant job and personal characteristics. In particular, employees in *learning* forms of work organisation, where they have a certain degree of discretion in the planning of their activities and time, are the least vulnerable. We also identify national policies which are likely to influence the individual probability of being vulnerable to non-employment in relation to the different forms of work organisation. Our first results suggest that active labour market policies amplify the protective effect of *Discretionary Learning*, while the characteristics of the industrial relations system, like centralisation of wage bargaining and employment protection legislation, favour the capacity of the *Constrained Learning* form of work organisation to secure employment.

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European policy-oriented research can and must deliver useful contributions to tackle the Europe 2020 challenges of Inclusive Growth. Key tools in this social sciences research are all types of data earning statistics, administrative social data, labour market data, surveys on quality of life or working conditions, policy indicators. The project aims to integrate and optimise these existing European data infrastructures and accompanying expertise.

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1. Introduction

Organisational restructuring has been widely observed in workplaces within OECD countries since the 1980s (Osterman (1994); Caroli and Van Reenen (2001); Greenan (2003)). These changes often pursue an objective of productivity growth and innovation in an attempt to restore or strengthen competitiveness for business survival in the face of a more and more competitive international economy. Indeed, work organisation is often considered a central element in fostering economic and business development in this new world. For example, Eurofound (2009) argues that some types of work organisation are associated with a better quality of work and employment and that their promotion may help in attaining the objectives set by the Europe 2020 strategy and the European Commission's 'New skills for new jobs' initiative. However, from the employees' perspective, while these new forms of work organisation may be an improvement in terms of job satisfaction - through more autonomy and task complexity - it may also be a source of deterioration of working conditions through increased stress and work pressure. In this paper, we are going to study an area of impact of new forms of work organisation which has seldom been considered: vulnerability to non-employment, which is defined as the probability of losing one's job and measured through the individual transition from employment to non-employment. Indeed, we argue that employees' ability to secure their employment in changing work environments is partly due to the form of work organisation in which they are employed. The acceptability for social partners of policies implemented to improve competitiveness in many OECD countries depends partly on this relationship on which little is known. As a matter of fact, most studies on labour market vulnerability focus on supply side factors which are much better documented than demand side factors in labour force surveys. In this regard, the purpose of the present paper is to provide an insight into the link between different forms of work organisation and the vulnerability of the workforce to non-employment within a number of countries taking part to the Programme for the Assessment of Adults Competencies (PIAAC) – a cross-country survey carried out by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD).

Different strands of literature relate work organization with economic outcomes. In the High Performance Work Systems (HPWS) literature a distinction between the hierarchical and flexible forms of work organisation is made, assessing the impact of organisational practices and work arrangements on efficiency improvements in production processes (Ichniowski et al. (1997); Osterman (1994); Gittleman et al. (1998); Wood (1999); Ramsay et al. (2000); Truss (2001)). The consequences of the diffusion of the Japanese lean production model associated with Toyota are also put to scrutiny in this research field (Womack, Jones and Roos (1990); MacDuffie and Pil (1997)). The literature on organisational design explores the relationship between work organisation and innovation and provides a more complex typology of forms of work

organisation, notably the distinction between different adhocratic work systems based on learning, problem solving and discretion (Burns and Stalker (1961); Mintzberg (1979, 1983); Lam (2005); Lam and Lundvall (2006); Lorenz and Lundvall (2010)). Finally, in the literature on job quality, the emphasis is mostly on the contrasted effects of the forms of work organisation on different aspects of working conditions (Karasek (1979); Clark (2005) and Green et al. (2015)). Many dimensions of the new forms of work organisation lead to increased job satisfaction and well-being, but some critical aspects like work intensity, lack of job control or poor physical work environment are sources of negative employee outcomes like stress, health impairments or work accidents. The effects of work organisation on labour market issues are barely covered in these research strands, although the job quality literature considers the effects of job insecurity on workers' job satisfaction, on their well-being or their health (Esser and Olsen (2011); De Witte (2005); Green (2015)). The few studies in the literature examining the determinants of job insecurity do not look at organisational aspects of work (Green et al. (2000)). Furthermore, while these studies approach the question of job insecurity using subjective measures of the concept, the present study proposes an objective one, exploiting the information given in the PIAAC survey regarding the employment history of employees.

In this paper, we use hierarchical cluster analysis to define five forms of work organisation based on the description given by employees of the tasks they perform. Vulnerability to non-employment is defined as being currently non-employed whilst having been employed at some point during the last twelve months previous the PIAAC survey. Then multilevel logistic regression is used to evaluate the impact of work organisation on vulnerability to non-employment in OECD countries participating in the first round of the PIAAC survey.

First results of our analysis are very instructive. It shows indeed a significant impact of work organisation on vulnerability to non-employment after controlling for relevant job characteristics and personal characteristics. In particular, employees in adhocratic forms of work organisation (Lam (2005)) characterised by a relatively high level of learning, problem solving and discretion are the least vulnerable to non-employment. We also identify national policies which are likely to influence the individual probability of being vulnerable to non-employment in relation to the different forms of work organisation. Our first results suggest that active labour market policies amplify the protective effect of *Discretionary Learning*, while the characteristics of the industrial relations system, like centralisation of wage bargaining and employment protection legislation, increase the capacity of the *Constrained Learning* form of work organisation, to secure employment.

The paper is organised as follows. The next two sections will familiarise the reader with the notions of vulnerability to non-employment and the different forms of work organisation. Then section IV presents the model and the variables used in our econometric analysis. Section V presents the empirical results before we conclude in section V.

2. Measuring vulnerability to non-employment

Several aspects of workforce vulnerability are described in the literature. It can be defined in terms of employment security, earnings, exposure to the workplace and social risks, occupational safety and health and treatment at the workplace (Weil (2009)). Employment security is considered by many as one of the most important aspect of the quality of a job and a major source of job satisfaction (Gallie (2003), Green (2006), Doellgast et al. (2009)). More generally the notion of workforce vulnerability is close to that of job insecurity. In literature job insecurity is defined in two manners: objective or subjective. The subjective definition refers mainly to the *perceived* fear of losing one's job (Anderson and Pontusson (2007), De Witte (2005), Esser and Olsen (2011)), or, more recently, to the possibility of a degradation of the job status, such as being transferred to a less interesting or less challenging post with the same employer or losing a valued feature of the job (Gallie et al. (2017), Green (2015)). As it refers to the *subjective* fear of losing one's job or one's job status, the responses are dependent on individual interpretations. The same objective situation could provoke feelings of insecurity for some even if, objectively, their job continuity is not affected and vice versa (De Witte (2005)). Many studies found, however, a link between the perception of job insecurity and individual's "objective" chances and position on the labour market (Clark and Postel-Vinay (2009), De Witte (2005)).

While the subjective job insecurity is about the *future*, the notion of objective job insecurity refers to the precariousness of the current employment relationship: part-time, temporary work, employment through temporary agency and self-employment (Saunders (2003)). This kind of employment is often associated with poor income and working conditions as well as greater exposure to economic risks. Nonstandard work (essentially temporary and part-time) has been on the rise in industrial countries since the late 1970s. Globalisation, technological change, as well as changes in patterns of family and work life are usually mentioned as principal explanation of such trends. However, not all "precarious" workers are vulnerable at every point of time. A dynamic perspective is usually necessary in order to better appreciate the degree of individual (objective) vulnerability. A temporary contract, for example, could be a "bridge" to a job with higher quality, but also a "trap" into precarious, low quality, short-term jobs. The interaction with the level and the duration of unemployment or inactivity is thus important. Vulnerable groups (such as young people, women, and low skilled workers) are often characterised by high incidence of unemployment rates as well as greater duration of unemployment spells. More generally worker flows among different labour market states (employment, unemployment, inactivity) are analysed¹. After defining the transition rates (for example, employment-employment,

¹ The concept of labour market vulnerability is quite large. It could include workers unable to access their statutory rights or lacking access to social protection (Saunders (2003)). Standard (full-time, indefinite) but low-paid work is also one of the forms of the labour market vulnerability. These kinds of vulnerabilities are out of the paper's scope.

employment-unemployment, employment-inactivity), the Markov transitions chains and Markov matrices are used for the descriptive analysis while regression analysis is usually applied in order to study the impact of main individual and institutional determinants of labour market transitions. From the theoretical point of view search and matching models are used (Pissarides (2000); Cahuc and Zylberberg (2004)).

Two main data sources are generally used to analyse labour mobility in European countries: LFS (Labour Force Survey) and EU-SILC (European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions). These databases allow defining different labour market transitions due to the panel data module and the detailed description of labour market activities. For example, the European Commission (2014) based on the research report of RWI - Leibniz Institute for Economic Research (2014) provides in-depth analysis of labour market transitions in the European Union before and during the economic downturn started in 2008. The report compares labour market transitions in the European Union in 2010 with transitions in 2006 and shows that employment stability has declined significantly in 2010 whereby a transition to unemployment was the most important destination upon leaving employment. During this period the transitions of men and young people were most strongly affected and temporary employment did not “bridge” any longer to a permanent contract (European Commission, 2014, p. 4). While EU-LFS and EU-SILC are certainly the main data sources for such analyses they contain no information about working conditions and work organisation².

Our notion of vulnerability relates to an objective definition of employment security namely the transition from employment to non-employment. While there are no questions about perceived worries about job loss in the PIAAC survey, the vulnerability of the workforce in terms of objective employment security can be measured. The concept that we refer to as vulnerability to non-employment hereafter is defined as the incapacity of employees to secure their employment in the near future. In this regard, it relates to the literature on the scarring effect of recurrent unemployment or more loosely on unemployment history (Disney (1979); Andress (1989); Gay (1989); Steiner (1989); Stern (1989); Winter-Ebmer and Zweimüller (1992); Arulampalam et al. (2001); Niang (2014)). In this literature, recurrent unemployment is considered as part of the cycle of labour market disadvantage and poverty in work. Spell recurrence is a cause of low-paid work and unstable jobs, as well as a sign of vulnerability to non-employment.

To implement our measure of vulnerability to non-employment, we thus employ data from the first round of the Programme for the Assessment of Adults Competencies (PIAAC) survey, which is a survey of adult skills carried out by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) in 23 OECD countries. The survey gathers information on adults’ skills proficiency and how those skills are used in the workplace and other environments, in addition to personal and job characteristics. The data collection has taken place between August 2011 and March 2012 in the national languages of the 23 participating countries. Due to missing data, we will ultimately keep only 19 out of the 23 countries in the econometric part of this current study. These

² Except in specific modules addressed to employees

nineteen countries are: Belgium (Flanders), Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Korea, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russian Federation, Slovak Republic, Spain, Sweden and United Kingdom (England and Northern Ireland). Austria, Canada and United States of America³ were removed, and Australia whose data were not available in the combined Public Use File (PUF).

This survey is very appropriate for the implementation of the measure of vulnerability to non-employment presented above as it offers a unique retrospective view into the employees' employment situation over a year. This has led to the definition of vulnerability presented here. We consider only individuals who are working or have worked in the last twelve months previous the survey. Those among them non-employed at the time of the survey, unless they are retired, are considered as vulnerable to non-employment compared to those who were able to keep their jobs. The resulting variable is our binary dependent variable. The original dataset has 157,642 observations, of which we keep only those individuals who declared having worked a paid job in the last 12 months preceding the survey (117,638). They represent roughly 74% of the initial number of observations in the survey as shown in Table 1 which synthesise the different steps in the construction of our vulnerability index.

[Table 1]

We remove from the sample young persons aged 16-24 in the initial cycle of studies, who amount to 11,176 persons. Among the remaining 106,462 individuals, we keep only employees. This leaves us with a sample of 91,895 individuals of which 7,565 (9%) are non-employed at the time of the survey for diverse reasons. We define our vulnerable group based on these reasons: end of temporary contract (24%), dismissals (10%), redundancy (10%), family responsibilities or child care (9%), study (4%), bad health (8%), resignation (5%), retirement at or after state pension age (6%), early retirement (3%), others (19%). We remove from the sample the persons retired at or after state pension and consider all the remaining individuals as hit by non-employment. They represent 8.5% of the considered population. Workers are more vulnerable to non-employment when they are not able to develop their skills in order to adapt to technological and organisational changes in the workplace and maintain their employability or when their working conditions do not allow them to remain in employment when they face personal challenges like family responsibility or health problems. Vulnerability to non-employment is also higher when the workplaces encounter problems that put their survival in jeopardy. For instance, when they are hit by an economic downturn or when they are not able to renew their strategy when new challengers arrive in their markets.

Figure 1 presents, for each country, our vulnerability rate as well as the unemployment rate calculated using PIAAC⁴ and the OECD unemployment rate based on the ILO

³ For these three countries, information was not given regarding the employment history of individuals. The type of employment contract was also not available for Canada and the United States. Information regarding the gender was unavailable for Austria, as well as information on the number of hours worked per week. The latter is also not available for Canada.

⁴ PIAAC unemployed is any person aged over 16 years old who is currently not employed, who has looked for a paid work at any time in the last 4 weeks, who has taken active steps to find a job and upon finding a job would have been able to start within 2 weeks or any person who will start a job within 3 months but is available to start a job within 2 weeks.

definition. Our vulnerability measure differs from the unemployment rate in many regards. The unemployment rate is calculated at a given point in time and considers the proportion of the active labour force without a paid work while the rate of vulnerability considers loosely the rate of job loss over a period of time. Therefore, it considers only those who have worked in the last 12 months.

[Figure 1]

The rate of unemployment is higher when the rate of job losses is higher even though all individuals leaving employment do not become unemployed. Indeed, leaving employment, individuals may transit toward inactivity. While the unemployment rate concerns those who are ready to return to work within two weeks, our measure of vulnerability includes those who do not qualify as unemployed for the many reasons given in Table 1. For instance, some people give up work, and for some of them, they do so in order to study. These persons are not considered as unemployed, while the training they receive is a concrete means of finding a new job. Others give up work for family responsibilities, for health reasons or for an early retirement. These people have been discouraged to remain in employment, although, with appropriate working conditions, could have remained employed. Thus the unemployment rate does not take into account all vulnerable persons on the labour market. On the other hand, the working age population who were unemployed or inactive during the previous twelve months is not taken into account in our indicator even though this population is certainly vulnerable in terms of income and well-being.

Spain is the country where all three measures of labour market vulnerability are the highest. In most countries the unemployment rate is greater than our vulnerability rate. The exceptions are Russia, Korea, Japan, the Nordic countries, Austria and Canada, where exit from the labour force is more frequent for employees who have not been able to secure their jobs. In what follows, we analyse these differences using multivariate multilevel modelling with a particular attention to different forms of work organisation as well as institutional contexts in terms of labour market policies.

3. Measuring forms of work organisation

Work organisation is a multidimensional concept. Eurofound's European Observatory of Working life (EurWORK) defines it as follows:

*"How work is planned, organised and managed – via production processes, job design, task allocation, rules, procedures, communication, responsibilities, management and supervisory styles, work scheduling, work pace, career development, decision-making processes, interpersonal and interdepartmental relationships."*⁵

Measuring work organisation usually consists of mapping different forms of work organisation based on their characteristics given in the High Performance Work System literature (HPWS) and the organisational design literature. The current study proposes a mapping of the forms of work organisation, building upon earlier work by Lorenz and Valeyre (2005) and Arundel et al. (2007). These two studies propose a mapping of forms of work organisation using the European Working Conditions Survey (EWCS). The choice of organisational variables in their mapping is based on the literature cited earlier. However, the approach used here is slightly different. First, it makes use of a different data source, which concerns OECD countries and not only European countries, but which is less informative in terms of the variables needed for the measurement of work organisation. Second, hierarchical cluster analysis is not applied to the scores of a factor analysis, but to the survey variables directly⁶. However, the clustering is made using the same ward's minimum variance hierarchical clustering method.

Interviewed employees in PIAAC are asked to describe the task they perform because it is considered as an indirect and objective measure of the use of skills in the workplace. These questions also capture some of the dimensions of work organisation. We select those that are available both for the current job and for the last job when the person is not currently employed. They cover the following dimensions:

- Discretion/autonomy in the job: how often the worker plans his/her own activities, organises his/her own time.
- Collaboration in the workplace, team work: how often the worker shares work-related information with a co-worker, cooperates with co-workers.
- Influence in the workplace: how often the worker persuades or influences other people in the workplace.

⁵ Retrieved from: <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/fr/observatories/eurwork/about-eurwork/work-organisation>

⁶ This choice is motivated first by the fact that we do not have that many variables, whereas the main reason factor analysis is used is to reduce the number of variables. Second, using the raw variables makes the interpretation easier than when using factor scores. In such a case, we have to interpret the result of the clustering based on the interpretation we have given to the results of the factor analysis. A third reason is related to the nature of our variables. They are ranked from the lowest frequency of skill use (never) to the highest (daily). Therefore the higher the frequency at which the task is performed, the higher the value assigned. This makes their assimilation to numerical variables acceptable, at least for a hierarchical cluster analysis. As for the indicator for on-the-job training, it also respects the same logic. It is higher for those who learn at work.

- Problem solving: how often the worker solves complex problems at work - requiring more than thirty minutes to find a solution.
- Formalisation: how often the worker uses his/her literacy skills at work to read directions and instructions.
- Learning through on-the-job training: whether the worker has the possibility through his job to improve his abilities and/or acquire new skills.

Each of the above variables, except "on-the-job training", are rated based on how often the task is performed as follows: 1 never, 2 less than once a month, 3 less than once a week but at least once a month, 4 at least once a week but not every day, 5 every day. The variable "on-the-job training" is a dummy variable indicating participation in on-the-job training activities.

Based on the above variables, we use Ward's hierarchical clustering to define a taxonomy of five forms of work organisation⁷: *Discretionary Learning*, *Constrained Learning*, *Independent*, *Simple* and *Taylorist*. The results resemble the ones obtained in Lorenz and Valeyre (2005) and Arundel et al. (2007). We find all the organisational settings identified in these two studies, except the lean production model. We have instead two other forms of work organisation: *Constrained Learning* and *Independent*. Table 2 gives the mean value for each of the variables according to the form of the work organisation. The last column of the table (overall) contains the mean of variables in the overall population⁸ regardless of the form of work organisation. For each form of work organisation and for each variable, a test of equality with the overall mean was performed. The bold figures indicate that the mean of the variable is significantly higher than the overall mean. The non-bold figures indicate lower mean value than the overall mean. For instance, in term of how often employees solve complex problems at work, employees working in a *Discretionary Learning* form of work organisation have a mean value of 3.70, which means (rounding up) that they perform this activity every week, while an average employee in the overall population performs it only monthly, with a mean of 2.87.

The bottom line of Table 2 shows the distribution of the different forms of work organisation in the overall population, which is representative of employees who have worked a paid job in the last 12 months and are not in the initial cycle of studies nor retired.

[Table 2]

The *Discretionary Learning* form account for roughly 30% of this population. It is characterised by the more frequent performance of all the tasks identified to map work organisation than in the overall population and in the other forms of work organisation, except in rare few cases. In this form of work organisation employees have a higher degree of autonomy in the way they do their job. They plan their own

⁷ The choice of the number of clusters has been made following Ward's minimum variance hierarchical clustering. A representation of a histogram of information losses resulting from regrouping clusters of the last merging steps of the hierarchy as well as a dendrogram to search for distinctive breaks (elbow) enables to settle on possible choices of cluster numbers. However, it is unclear as to how much information losses are tolerable. We therefore adopted a practical solution based on previous studies and retained a number of clusters that makes more sense (interpretable), after a thorough review based on their mapping across countries or groups of countries and their respective institutions. Also, note that individuals for whom some of the variables used in the clustering are missing are assigned afterwards to the classes they are the closest based on available information, maximising the interclass variance and minimising the intraclass variance.

⁸ The population we are interested in here is composed of employees who have worked in the last 12 months preceding the survey, are not youth (16-24) in initial cycle studies and are not retired.

activities and organise their own time on a daily basis. They are also more frequently involved in solving complex problems at work: at least once a week, compared to once a month in the average population. Except for the *Taylorist* form of work organisation, they are more involved in team work than employees in the other forms of work organisation. As a matter of fact, they share work related information on a daily basis and cooperate or collaborate with co-workers at least every week. They are also more involved in taking initiative as they persuade or influence people at work on a weekly basis. They read directions or instructions at least every week. Finally, they are more involved in learning activities. Nearly 90% of them receive on-the-job training. This form of work organisation resembles the one of the same name in Arundel et al. (2007) and the operating adhocracy in Lam (2005).

The clustering identifies another learning form of work organisation referred to as *Constrained Learning* because more constraints weigh on the organisation of work. Unlike in the *Discretionary Learning* form of work organisation, employees in the *Constrained Learning* form experience below average frequencies for planning their own activities (less than once a month), solving complex problems (less than once a week, but at least once a month) and persuading or influencing people (less than once a week but at least once a month). However, they organise their own time weekly, share work-related information daily, cooperate or collaborate with co-workers weekly, read direction or instruction weekly and 53 % of them are involved in on-the-job training. This form of work organisation differs from the *Discretionary Learning* in term of discretion, problem solving and influence at work, but employees have more learning opportunities than in other forms of work organisation through collaborations and sharing of information as well as through on-the-job training.

The *Independent* form of work organisation is below the overall mean for reading directions or instructions (less than once a week, but at least once a month) and on-the-job training. Only 3% of them are involved in learning activities at work. They are situated above the overall mean for the other variables. They plan their own activities and organise their own time daily; they solve complex problems, at least once a month but less than once a week; they share work-related information daily and cooperate or collaborate with co-workers at least once a month but less than once a week; they persuade or influence people once a month but less than once a week. This form of work organisation differs from the *Discretionary Learning* form in terms of formalisation of work and learning opportunities. Employees in these forms of organisations have a lot of discretion and many opportunities to exchange with other people in professional networks but their organisation is more informal.

The *simple form* of work organisation is opposite to the *Discretionary Learning* form as employees perform less frequently than in the average population all the listed tasks. Thus, they perform more simple jobs in more simple organisations. However, in this form of work organisation, 14% of employees receive on the job training, which is more than in the *Independent* form.

The last form of work organisation (*Taylorism*) is characterised by below average frequency for all listed tasks except for two of them: cooperating or collaborating and sharing work-related information. 25% of employees in this form receive on-the-job training, which is more than in the *Independent* and *Simple* forms, but less than in the *Learning* forms of work organisation. Thus, employees perform simple tasks in more

structured organisations than in the *Simple* form. This is why we identify this last form as the Taylorist form of work organisation.

Figure 2 below gives the mapping of these five organisational forms of OECD countries covered in PIAAC. The *Discretionary Learning* form is more frequent in the Nordic and Anglo-Saxon countries. In these countries the percentage of persons working in a *Discretionary Learning* form of organisation is above the overall percentage. It is over 30% for the following countries: Finland, United Kingdom, United States, Ireland, Canada, Denmark, the Netherlands, the Czech Republic, Estonia, Belgium and Sweden. For the *Constrained Learning* form of work organisation, only Germany, United States, Japan and Canada are above the overall percentage. The *Independent* form of organisation is mostly found in the Mediterranean, Northern and Asian countries. The following countries are above average: Sweden, Italy, Norway, France, Poland, Russia, Austria, Estonia, Denmark, Slovakia, Belgium, Spain, Czech Republic, Canada and Korea. The *Simple* form of work organisation is found within countries such as Russia, Korea, Italy, Japan, Spain, France and Belgium. The *Taylorist* form is relatively more spread in countries such as Slovakia, Japan, Austria, France, Ireland, Germany, Spain and Norway.

[Figure 2]

One can distinguish at least four groups of countries according to the prevailing configurations of forms of work organisation. There is a first group of countries composed of Finland, United Kingdom, Netherlands, United States, Ireland and Canada. In these countries, the *Learning* forms of work organisation are predominant, especially the *Discretionary Learning* organisation. A second group is composed of countries where the *Independent* and the *Discretionary Learning* forms of work organisation are predominant, especially the former. These countries are: Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Norway, Poland, and Sweden. The fourth group is composed of Austria, Spain, France, Italy, Japan, Korea, Russia and Slovakia. The predominant forms of work organisation in these countries are Taylorist, Independent and Simple, especially the latter one and the first one. The last group is made of only Germany, where the *Constrained Learning* form of work organisation is incredibly high compared to the other countries.

Figure 3 below shows the differences in forms of work organisation across industries. A first look of Figure 3 shows a marked contrast between the *Discretionary Learning* form of work organisation and the *Taylorist* and *Simple* forms. Services activities are predominant in the *Discretionary Learning* form, whereas primary and secondary activities are found predominantly in the *Taylorist* and *Simple* forms of work organisation. A closer look at the service industries shows further differences. The dynamic (financial, insurance and real estate activities, information and communication) and welfare (education, health and social work, and public administration) services have more frequent *Discretionary Learning* forms than the non-dynamic services (hotels and restaurants; wholesale and retail trade; and other community, social, and personal services). Unlike the non-dynamic and welfare services, the dynamic ones are characterised by a relatively high level of ICT intensity, productivity growth and international trade (Wren et al. (2013)). Furthermore, the

Discretionary Learning form is more frequent in large-sized firms, whereas the *Simple* and *independent* form of work organisation are predominant in small-sized establishments.

The *Constrained Learning* form is more widespread in welfare services such as health and social work or public administration. The *Independent* organisation is more typical of agriculture, forestry and fishing, administrative and support service activities, transportation and storage and activities of households. Finally, the spread across industries in the *Taylorist* form of work organisation is the opposite picture of what is observed in the *Discretionary Learning* form.

[Figure 3]

Figure 4 shows the differences in forms of work organisation across occupations. There is also a clear contrast here between *Taylorist* and *Discretionary Learning* forms of work organisation. The *Discretionary Learning* form is more frequent in occupations such as: armed forces; legislators, senior officials and managers; professionals; technicians and associate professionals. On the other hand, the *Taylorist* form is more widespread in elementary occupations; skilled agricultural and fishery workers; plant and machine operators and assemblers; craft and related trades workers; service workers and shop and market sales workers; clerks.

The *Constrained Learning* form of work organisation is more typical of clerks; and service workers and shop and market sales workers. Legislators, senior officials and managers; clerks; technicians and associate professionals; and professionals more often experience the *Independent* form when elementary occupations; plant and machine operators and assemblers; skilled agricultural and fishery workers; service workers and shop and market sales workers; craft and related trades workers more often work according to the *Taylorist* form.

[Figure 4]

The aim of the current paper is to analyse the relationship between work organisation and the vulnerability to non-employment. In this regard, Table 3 gives the distribution of the forms of work organisation for both the vulnerable and non-vulnerable employees. The form of work organisation characterises the current work for non-vulnerable employees, the tasks performed in the last work for vulnerable employees. Again, a strong contrast between the *Discretionary Learning* and the *Taylorist* forms of work organisation appears. The vulnerable employees are relatively more present in the *Taylorist* forms of work organisations (23% versus 15% for non-vulnerable persons), whereas the *Discretionary Learning* form is predominant among the non-vulnerable employees (31% versus 15% for vulnerable employees). Vulnerable employees are also more frequent in the *Independent* and *Simple* forms of work organisation (respectively 33% and 17% against 28% and 14% for non-vulnerable employees).

[Table 3]

4. Model and variables

This section presents the (multilevel) logistic model and both individual- and country-level variables. Researchers in social sciences are more and more interested in research questions concerning how outcomes at the individual level can be seen as the result of the interplay between individual and contextual factors. Indeed, differences in individual outcomes could reflect differences in the effects of country-specific characteristics such as labour markets or other socioeconomic institutions. The studies based on multilevel models have proliferated during the last two decades with the focus on different topics such as educational outcomes (O’Connell and McCoach, 2008), in-work poverty (Andress and Lohmann (2008)) or quality of working life (Greenan et al. (2013)). Explaining the incidence of job market vulnerability cannot be analysed without taking into account not only the individual and employer characteristics but also the institutional context. In this section, after describing the empirical model we define the variables used in estimations.

4.1 Model

In this paper, the sample comes from the PIAAC data and contains the employed persons from 19 OECD countries. This kind of multi-country data set offers the possibility to quantify the extent to which differences in individual outcomes (here vulnerability) reflect differences in the effects of country-specific characteristics, which are different from effects associated with variations in the characteristics of the individuals themselves (Bryan and Jenkins (2016)). How to “uncover” these country effects?

We start with the standard logistic regression model with country fixed effects (estimated as the coefficients attached to country binary variables). Each country intercept represents the effects of unobserved factors that are shared within each country.

Let us consider v the dependent variable, vulnerability to non-employment. It is a binary variable equal to one if the person is vulnerable to non-employment and zero otherwise. Let us denote p , the probability of being vulnerable ($p = Prob(v = 1)$). Let us consider c_k , a k form of work organisation, k ranging from 1 to 5, for our five forms of work organisation defined above. It takes the value 1 if the person works or has worked in a k form of work organisation. Let us consider that x contains all the other socioeconomic and job characteristics that we use as controls and z all the country-level variables. Model 1 can be expressed as follows:

$$\pi_{ij} = \log\left(\frac{p_{ij}}{1 - p_{ij}}\right) = \beta_1 + \sum_{k=2}^5 \beta_k c_{kij} + \beta_6 x_{ij} + F_j \quad (1)$$

where π_{ij} is the odds ratio of individual i in country j , F_j represents the country fixed effects introduced to deal with the hierarchical nature of our data, which results in intra-country correlations. β_1 and the β_k s are scalars, while β_6 is a vector containing the coefficient attached to the control variables in x .

The drawback of this method is that the country institutional contexts could not be explicitly introduced (Bryan and Jenkins (2016)). Country effects are considered fixed and therefore only available for countries in the sample. The results of the estimates cannot be extended to other countries. Moreover, if institutional contexts shape the individual behaviours, outcomes are likely to be correlated within countries (Greenan et al. (2014)). The standard error estimates are downwardly biased (Hox (2010); Bryan and Jenkins (2016)). As it was mentioned above, respondents in the PIAAC survey are employed persons from 19 OECD countries. Thus, the dataset is hierarchical, with a level 1 (the individual, indexed by i) nested in a level 2 (the country, indexed by j). The hierarchical structure of the dataset as well as possible correlations across observations within the countries could be taken into account in a multilevel model which enables to obtain statistically efficient estimates of regression coefficients and correct standard errors (Hox (2010)).

Within the multilevel modelling frame, we estimated two models. The first model is a multilevel logistic model with country random effects in the constant term (“random intercept”) as well as in four individual-level fixed effects representing the different forms of work organisation (“random slopes” model). We suppose that belonging to one of the form of work organisation does not have the same effect according to national contexts. The random slope model allows the effect of indicators of form of work organisation to vary across countries.

The random effect model considers that country effects are distributed randomly (usually normally) across countries. This makes it possible to extend our results to other countries. Assuming that the different random terms are not correlated, the model can be expressed as follows:

$$\pi_{ij} = \log\left(\frac{p_{ij}}{1 - p_{ij}}\right) = \beta_{1j} + \sum_{k=2}^5 \beta_{kj} c_{kij} + \beta_6 x_{ij} \quad (2)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_{1j} &= \gamma_1 + r_{1j} \\ \beta_{kj} &= \gamma_k + r_{kj} \end{aligned}$$

with $r_{1j} \rightarrow N(0, \sigma_1^2)$ and $r_{kj} \rightarrow N(0, \sigma_k^2)$ for $k = 2, 3, 4, 5$ (the first form, *Taylorism* is taken as the reference form of work organisation). The slope of the linear relationship between the form of work organisation indicator and the log-odds of being vulnerable is thus $\gamma_k + r_{kj}$ for country j . This model is estimated with and without Russia in the sample. As country-level variables are not available for this country, we deem it necessary to estimate the country random effects without Russia in order to have a comparison basis with the model with the country-level variables and their interactions with the different forms of work organisation.

A particular advantage of multilevel modelling is the ability to explore the effects of group-level predictors i.e. introduce explicitly the country-level explanatory factors in the model. It allows to identify the contextual effects as well as cross-level interactions. So our second multilevel logistic model goes further and introduces country-level

variables and their interactions with the different forms of work organisation so that the four individual-level predictors vary with the size of country-level fixed effects (cross-level interaction).

The interaction effects allow the effect of one explanatory variable on the outcome to depend on the value of another explanatory variable. We suppose, for example, that the effect of belonging to one of the forms of work organisation on the probability of being vulnerable to non-employment depends on the mix of the country-level labour market policies and wage bargaining practices.

In order to do so, we extend the model in equation 2 to take into consideration country-level variables in z . This version of the multilevel logistic model considers that the contextual variables in z can explain the national differences mentioned earlier. It can be written as follows:

$$\pi_{ij} = \log\left(\frac{p_{ij}}{1-p_{ij}}\right) = \beta_{1j} + \sum_{k=2}^5 \beta_{kj}c_{kij} + \beta_6x_{ij} \quad (3)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_{1j} &= \gamma_1 + \gamma_{11}z_j + r_{1j} \\ \beta_{kj} &= \gamma_k + \gamma_{k1}z_j + r_{kj} \end{aligned}$$

with $r_{1j} \rightarrow N(0, \sigma_1^2)$ and $r_{kj} \rightarrow N(0, \sigma_k^2)$ for $k = 2, 3, 4, 5$. γ_{11} and γ_{k1} s are vectors of parameters attached to the country-level variables. Country level variables are centered so that the intercept gives the odds of the reference individual when the macro variables are at their mean value.

However, one needs to be very cautious when interpreting the results from the model in equation 3. There is an issue regarding the reliability of estimates from a multilevel logistic regression in relation to the number of subjects at level 2 (see e.g. Austin (2010), Moineddin et al. (2011), Stegmueller (2013) and Bryan and Jenkins (2016)). Bryan and Jenkins (2016) concluded that when this number is lower than 30, the estimates of the variance component and their standard errors are biased downward, and we need more than 30 when cross-level interactions are included. This issue is further discussed in the empirical analysis.

4.2 Variables

What are the main driving forces behind the individual and country differences in vulnerability to non-employment? We combine micro data on individuals coming from the PIAAC survey with macro data describing the institutional context. At the individual level, we retain job characteristics and personal characteristics defined using raw or derived variables from the background questionnaire of the PIAAC survey, which is very rich. At country level, we have labour market policy variables as well as the institutional characteristics of trade unions and wage settings, the structure of economic sectors, the GDP growth rates and expenditures on R&D. The distribution of individual and job characteristics variables across vulnerable and non-vulnerable individuals is presented in table A1 in appendix.

4.2.1 Job and employer characteristics

As for the job and employer characteristics, we are able to measure:

- Economic sector: private, public and nonprofit sectors

- Establishment size: lower or equal to 10, between 11 and 50, between 51 and 250, between 251 and 1000, more than 1000, and a dummy variable for missing values.
- Industry classification: 16 categories and a dummy for missing values.
- Occupational classification: 10 indicator variables based on the International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO).
- Number of hours worked per week as a continuous variable.
- Type of employment contract: indefinite versus temporary and other types of employment contracts.
- An indicator for the use of Information and Communication technologies (ICT) in the workplace.

Table A1 shows that there are no striking differences in the distribution of the two groups of non-vulnerable and vulnerable across private, public and non-profit organisations, that individuals in small-sized firms are more likely to be vulnerable to non-employment (1-50 employees), that there are minor differences in the distribution of the two groups across industries. There is a relatively higher vulnerability in elementary and semi-skilled occupations in the service sector and agriculture (ISCO 9, 5, 6). As expected, there is more vulnerability to non-employment for persons with precarious employment contract (temporary contract, temporary employment agency contract, apprenticeship or other training scheme, no contract, other employment relation). Finally, there are relatively more vulnerable to non-employment among persons who do not use a computer at work.

4.2.2 Sociodemographic characteristics

We consider first all socioeconomic variables characterising the individuals before their entry in the labour market. Based on the results of a pre-analysis of the personal determinants of vulnerability to non-employment, we retain the following variables:

- Age: ten year bands for under 24, 25-34, 35-44, 45-54, over 55.
- Education: using the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED), we consider three indicator variables for primary or less (ISCED level 1 or less: early childhood and primary education), secondary (ISCED level 2 to 4: lower, upper and post-secondary non-tertiary education) and university education (ISCED level 5 to 8: doctoral, master, bachelor and short cycle tertiary education).
- Gender
- Marital status: single, using persons living with a spouse or partner as the reference category
- Family responsibilities: no children, 1 child, 2 children and 3 children and more.
- Social background: we have here the immigration status and the education level of the parents. We have three indicator variables for first generation immigrants, second generation immigrants, and non 1st or 2nd generation immigrant as the reference category. A first generation immigrant is a person who is foreign-born and whose parents (or at least one parent) are foreign-born; A second generation immigrant a native-born person with foreign-born parents.

- Dummy variables for our 19 countries.

Table A1 shows that vulnerable individuals are mostly single young females with secondary education. They more often have either no children or three children or more, are first generation immigrants and have uneducated parents.

4.2.3 Institutional and economic factors

Different institutional factors are likely to influence the individual probability of being vulnerable to non-employment. What are the national characteristics potentially important in the explanation of the national differences in countries' vulnerability profile?

It is usually considered that institutional features, such as unemployment benefits, degree of employment protection, as well as active labour market policies are important in order to explain labour market transitions (Bassanini and Duval, 2006, 2009). However, theoretical considerations about the effects of labour market institutions on labour market transitions generally concern the discussion about the impact of labour market institutions on incentives to supply labour at any given market wage (European Commission (2014)). So it is most of the time the transition out of unemployment to employment which is implicitly considered⁹. In particular, active labour market policies (active LMP) are generally defined as measures which assist the inactive and unemployed to find a job with the objective to bring more people into the labour force and into jobs. However, the active LMP also favour general employability of individuals and thus contribute to the job stability and decreased individual vulnerability to non-employment. For instance, programmes such as employment maintenance incentives which aim to facilitate continuing employment in situations of restructuring or workplace training programs are integral part of active policies as defined by the OECD. Furthermore, labour market institutions could influence firms' choices of organisational designs. Holm et al. (2010) as well as Holm and Lorenz (2015) show that strong systems of unemployment protection combined with an emphasis on active labour market policies are predictors of the likelihood of the discretionary learning forms of work organisation.

We have retained the following variables characterising national labour market policies¹⁰:

- Share of active LMP in total expenditures on labour market policies. When it is higher, the share of passive LMP is lower.

⁹ For some kinds of labour market policies such as unemployment insurance benefits the transitions out of non-participation are also considered (for example, with higher unemployment benefits the "non actives" would increase their labour market participation in order to become eligible for unemployment benefits).

¹⁰ The total expenditures on labour market policies is partitioned into expenditures in two types of labour market policies: active and passive. The active policies are: public employment services and administration; training; employment incentives; sheltered and supported employment and rehabilitation; direct job creation; start-up incentives. The passive policies are: out-of-income maintenance and support and early retirement. The reader can refer to the OECD database for more details about these elements of the expenditures on labour market policies. As it can be seen, we considered in the current analysis only 3 active LMP. This choice has been made to reduce the number of country-level variables in the multilevel model in order to have more reliable estimates. However, a thorough analysis of the data has been performed (using correlation analysis and principal component analysis) regarding all country-level variables to select the ones presented here. These variables turn out to summarize the essential aspects of the different institutions and economies across OECD countries relevant to the current analysis, avoiding information redundancies.

- Share of expenditures in training, employment incentives and start-up incentives in active LMP. The expenditures in this ratio contribute to maintaining employability and/or employment. When it is higher, the share of public employment services and administration, sheltered and supported employment and rehabilitation and direct job creation expenditures is lower.
- Share out-of-work income maintenance and support expenditures in passive LMP. When it is higher, the share of early retirement expenditure is lower.

In addition to expenditures on labour market policies, we also take into account the degree of strictness of employment protection legislation and the centralisation of wage bargaining. More precisely, we introduce OECD indicators on the strictness of employment protection legislation concerning individual and collective dismissals of employees in regular employment as well as use of temporary employment. Two indicators are used. They measure respectively the procedures and costs involved in dismissing individuals or groups of workers and the procedures involved in hiring workers on fixed-term or temporary work agency contracts. For each year, indicators refer to the regulation in force on the 1st of January. The data range from 0 to 6 with higher scores representing stricter regulation. Higher costs and more complex procedures in dismissing individuals favour job stability (OECD (2004), Bassanini and Garnero (2013)). The centralisation of wage bargaining is reflected by a summary measure taking into account both union density and bargaining coverage at multiple levels. According to Calmfors and Driffill (1988) countries with highly centralised and highly decentralised wage bargaining have lower unemployment than countries with an intermediate degree of centralisation. Recent empirical evidence has shown that this relationship has become weaker together with the loss of union influence and stresses the need to take into account the diversity of labour market institutions (Aidt and Tzannatos (2002)).

Finally, the sectoral structure, the country innovation performance as well as the macroeconomic conditions are reflected in the share of employment in services, R&D expenditure as a percentage of GDP and GDP growth rate.

The variables retained come from either the OECD database or the database on institutional characteristics of trade unions, wage settings, state interventions and social pacts 1960-2014 (ICTWSS) from Jelle Visser of Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Labour Studies. They are displayed in Table 4.

[Table 4]

5. Results

5.1 Fixed and random effects

All models estimate a weighted logistic regression of the probability of being vulnerable to non-employment, using the survey sample weights. For comparison purposes, we start with a simple logistic model with country fixed effects (Model 1). Then we estimate three multilevel models. Model 2a is a random slope logit regression in which we allow the constant term of the model and the effects of working in other forms of work organisation than *Taylorism*, which is the reference form of work organisation in the regressions, to vary randomly across countries. Model 2b is the same as Model 2a but estimated without Russia. Finally, Model 3, in addition to Model 2b, considers country-level variables as well as their interactions with the different forms of work organisation. This allows us to explain observed differences between countries in the response variable and the effects of work organisation.

The results are given in tables 5, 6 and table A2 in the appendix. Table 5 shows the results of the estimation of the four different models for our variables of interest, the indicators of forms of work organisation, and the random parts of the multilevel models. Table 6 reports the estimates for country-level variables and cross-level interactions. Finally, table A2 in the appendix shows the estimation of individual fixed effects.

[Table 5]

Comparing the simple logistic regression with the three multilevel models, the conclusions about the effect of our variables of interest and most of the individual fixed effect do not change: the sign and significance coefficients remain stable¹¹. The simple logit model confirms the existence of country effect as the great majority of the country-fixed effects are highly significant. Compared to France twelve countries have a different vulnerability profile while there is no difference only in six countries (Czech Republic, Finland, Italy, Japan, Slovakia and Sweden). Models 2a and 2b estimate a multilevel logistic regression model of the probability of being vulnerable to non-employment, with a country random intercept and random slopes for forms of work organisation. The difference between two models is the absence of Russia in the model 2b.

The estimates of the variance of the random terms, given in the lower part of Table 5, show considerable variation of the estimates of the constant term and the coefficient

¹¹The value of coefficients between simple logit and random intercept and slope multilevel models are not easily comparable because of change of scaling due to the introduction of random effects. It is argued that coefficients from a random intercept model should be greater in magnitude than coefficients from its single-level version, provided that the distribution of each explanatory variable is the same across groups. It should be also noted here that the coefficients from multilevel models have now a “cluster-specific interpretation” i.e. within the same country while the coefficients from single-level models have a “population averaged (or marginal) interpretation.”

attached to the different forms of work organisation across countries. The intercept variance of 0.162 in model 2b is interpreted as the between-country variance in the log-odds of being vulnerable for a reference individual living in an average OECD country, while the slope variation of *Discretionary Learning* of 0.092, for example, is the between-country variance in the effect of *Discretionary Learning* on the probability of being vulnerable.

Comparing model 2a and model 2b (with and without Russia), while the relation and significance of forms of work organisation do not change, some individual fixed effects become significant in model 2b (without Russia) compared to model 2a (with Russia) and vice versa (cf. Table A2 in Appendix). For example, while the impact of working in agriculture, in administrative and support service activities and in education is not significantly different compared to manufacturing in model 2 with Russia, these effects become significant without it: compared to manufacturing, working in agriculture, in administrative service activities and education significantly increases the probability of being vulnerable. Without Russia, the protective effect of working as a legislator or professional appears while the coefficient on craft and related trades workers becomes nonsignificant.

Finally, as it was mentioned in the previous section, the multilevel modelling allows not only to identify the country-effect, but also to “explain” it by taking into account the variables characterising country-level specificities. It is indeed important not only to know whether there are differences between countries, but also to know the factors (political, social, etc.) behind these differences. For instance, we would like to know the reason why the effect of working in a given form of work organisation, for example, *Discretionary Learning*, on the probability of being vulnerable to non-employment is different in France from that observed in Germany. Is it because of the difference in the way they handle labour market issues, for instance their labour market policies? In order to answer such questions, we have to extend model 2b to include country-level variables that can explain these differences as well as their interaction with the different forms of work organisation. By introducing the cross-level interaction terms between the forms of work organisation indicators and macroeconomic variables, we thus analyse if institutional conditions reinforce or, on the contrary, moderate the impact of the forms of work organisation on an individual’s vulnerability to non-employment.

This is what we do with model 3, which estimates are given in Table 5¹². First of all the unobserved variations of the random terms in model 3 reduces considerably compared to model 2 (cf. Table 5). Therefore, we may say that our country-level variables explain almost all the observed heterogeneity between countries in the rate of vulnerability and the effect of forms of work organisation. For instance, if there is a difference between France and Germany in the effects of *Discretionary Learning* on vulnerability to non-employment, this could be explained by the differences in their spendings on active labour market policies, the structure of those spendings and the spendings on out-of-income maintenance and support.

¹²The only critical aspect of model 2 and 3 is the number of subjects at level 2. We have only 18 countries. As always with this type of analysis, we face some asymptotic issues when the number of countries is small.

5.2 The impact of the forms of work organisation and country-level heterogeneity

The top panel of table 5 gives the coefficients associated with the intercept and the four forms of work organisation, *Taylorism* being the reference category. The intercept gives the probability of being vulnerable to non-employment for the reference individual of each model: a young male worker (under 24) with primary education or less, no children, native since two generations, with educated parents, working in the private sector with an indefinite contract, performing an elementary occupation in a *Taylorist* form of work organisation implying no use of ICT in a manufacturing establishment with less than 10 employees, working an average number of hours per week. In model 1, this reference employee is French and his chances of making a transition to non-employment is 17.5%¹³, about twice the average vulnerability in the overall population (cf. Table 1 in section II). Working in an *Independent* form of work organisation would not change this result as the corresponding coefficient is non-significant. But if this reference employee had experienced a *Discretionary Learning* form of work organisation his odds of being non-employed would be much lower, amounting to 9%¹⁴ which is close to average vulnerability. In a *simple* form, it would be 13.4% and 14.1% in a *Constrained Learning* form. The results in models 2a and 2b remain close to those found in model 1, except that the coefficient associated with the *Constrained Learning* form of work organisation becomes smaller than the *Simple* form, implying that the odds of being non-employed are lower¹⁵. The hierarchy in the impact of forms of work organisation remains unchanged in model 3: the *Discretionary Learning* form is the form of work organisation where vulnerability to non-employment is the lowest, followed by the *Constrained Learning* form and the *Simple* form, the odds of the *Independent* form being similar to those of the *Taylorist* form. More precisely a person working in a *Discretionary Learning* organisation reduces by more than a half (56%) his/her chance of being vulnerable to non-employment, compared to another person working in a *Taylorist* organisation. These percentages are 22% et 23% for persons in *Constrained Learning* or *Simple* forms of work organisation, respectively.¹⁶

Some forms of work organisation are thus more efficient than others for maintaining employability and securing employment. We have to keep in mind that although the regressions are cross-sectional, they implicitly compare two different points in time (now and sometime in the last twelve months) and they are obtained using a very large set of controls taking into account sociodemographic characteristics including migration status and parents' levels of education, employment relations characteristics and detailed occupations and industry (cf. Table A2 in the appendix). We thus hope to be the closest possible to a pure work organisation effect. We find that the *Discretionary Learning* and the *Constrained Learning* forms of work organisation that favour skills development through on-the-job training, knowledge sharing, problem solving and job discretion are more efficient at securing employment than forms of work organisation where employees perform simple tasks and lack discretion that would allow them to take advantage of learning opportunities like in *Taylorist* organisations or lack access to

¹³This predicted probability is calculated using the following formula : $1/(1+\exp(1.429))$

¹⁴ $1/(1+\exp(1.429+0.756))$

¹⁵ This is because in multilevel models the relationship is not an evaluation in reference country (France in our case) at any given country.

¹⁶ In order to obtain the percentage of variation in the odds of being vulnerable for one unit change in explanatory variable we use the following formula: $100 \times \{ \exp(\beta_k) - 1 \}$

organised on-the-job training like in the *Independent* organisations or lack opportunities to share knowledge with their co-workers like in *Simple* organisations.

As for individual fixed effects, the great majority of significant results are compatible with the literature on labour market insecurity measured by the transition rate between employment and unemployment (for example, Duhautois et al. (2014)).

Our results show (cf. Table A2 in the appendix) that women are significantly more vulnerable to non-employment than men. Vulnerability to non-employment increases significantly for very young workers (aged under 24) while individuals aged between 35 and 54 have the lowest probability to be vulnerable. More educated workers are more protected against vulnerability to non-employment. Higher education generally implies higher job stability (Charlot and Malherbet (2013)). However, the significance level is only 10% (in multilevel specifications). The type of the contract (temporary versus indefinite) increases strongly the probability of being vulnerable to non-employment. An important number of temporary jobs in an economy lead to both a higher level of job creation and job destruction. Job destruction of temporary employment is particularly important during economic recessions. The end of a temporary contract which is not renewed is an important factor of vulnerability to non-employment. Controlling for education, the use of ICT at work decreases the probability of losing a job. Vulnerability is also lower in bigger establishments. Compared to manufacturing, other service activities is the only sector associated with a reduced probability of being vulnerable. Finally, compared to elementary occupations, “white-collar” occupations like legislators, professionals and technicians, but also “blue collar” occupations like plant and machine operators decrease the probability of being vulnerable.

Table 6 reports the estimated effects in model 3 of the country-level and cross-level interactions¹⁷ on the probability of being vulnerable to non-employment. By construction, the direct effects of the macroeconomic indicators (column 1) reflect the impact of institutional contexts on the reference individual who is working in the *Tayloristic* form of work organisation. The significant effects are all positive except the GDP growth rate. Compared to all other forms of work organisation, the spendings on active LMP as well as their structure are associated with a higher level of vulnerability for workers employed in *Tayloristic* organisations. Active labour market policies are less efficient at securing employment in *Tayloristic* organisations than in other forms of work organisations (except *Simple* forms) and in particular when they focus on training, employment incentives and start-up incentives. The impact of economic growth is negative as expected. The economic recession leads to job destructions especially for the simple jobs found in *Taylorist* organisation. Such organisations choose to reduce their hiring activities and increase dismissals. As they have not invested in skills building or organisational learning, their labour force is mainly substitutable. Therefore flows from employment to unemployment or to inactivity are increased. On the contrary, as soon as the recovery is back, they hire new workers on temporary short-term contracts.

¹⁷ As stated earlier, studies investigating the reliability of multilevel model estimates in relation to the number of subjects in level 2 suggest using at least 30 subjects at level 2 when we introduce level 2 variables and cross-level interactions. In the current study, we have only 18 countries, and, unfortunately, despite our efforts to reduce the number of country-level variables, we were left with 9 country-level variables. In order to make sure that our estimates were not affected, the multilevel model has been estimated, introducing one country-level variable at a time. The results of this robustness check show no significant differences compared to the results when all variables are included. More importantly, we obtain the same signs for all significant coefficient estimates. However, we lose significance for some estimates, which confirm that the standard errors downward biases when all country-level variables are included in the estimation. Results are available on request.

The interpretation of the estimated parameter of the cross-level interactions (columns 2 to 5) is different from the direct effect on column 1. Here, the country-level variables are moderating the effects of the variables they are interacted with. Starting with the *Discretionary Learning* form of work organisation, given the negative direct effect of this form of work organisation (table 5, model 3), a positive estimate on the interaction term means that the country-level variable in question reduces the protective effect of *Discretionary Learning* compared with *Taylorism* while the negative sign of the interaction term means that the given policy amplifies its beneficial effect. We find that the percentage of out-of-income maintenance and support in passive LMP expenditures reduce the protective effect of the *Discretionary Learning* form of work organisation when active LMP have the opposite moderating effect. The higher the % of active LMP and the shares of training and employment incentives in active LMP expenditure, the more efficient are *Discretionary Learning* organisations in preventing transitions to non-employment for their employees. The interaction terms with strictness of employment protection legislation are also negative but not significant.

To illustrate these results, we could calculate the effect of *Discretionary Learning* on the log-odds of being vulnerable for different values of macroeconomic variables. For example, in Korea only 6% of all active LMP go to training while this indicator is 53% in Denmark (cf. table 4). So for Korea the effect of *Discretionary Learning* compared with *Taylorism* will be: $-0.810 - (0.942 * 0.06) = -0.867$; while in Denmark it will be: $-0.810 - (0.942 * 0.53) = -1.309$ ¹⁸. The differences are even amplified with the expenditures on employment incentives. The same calculations show that the effect of *Discretionary Learning* on the log-odds of being vulnerable will be -0.823 in the UK, where these expenditures represent only one percent of active LMP while it will be -1.61 for Sweden that spends 64% of its active LMP on employment incentives¹⁹. Like with *Discretionary Learning*, the share of passive LMP dedicated to out of income maintenance and support increases the vulnerability of the workforce in *Independent* forms of work organisations. On the contrary, the interaction effects of variables reflecting the structure of expenditures on active policies are negative and significant. While the direct effect of *Independent* forms of work organisation is negative, but not significant, implying that it is similar to that of *Taylorist* organisation, the significant protective effect of this form of work organisation appears in interaction with active LMP. First, we find, like in *Discretionary Learning* organisations, that interactions with share of active LMP expenditures on training as well as employment incentives are negative. A drawback of *Independent* forms of work organisations is that it is the form where on-the-job training is the lowest. Active LMPs targeted at training seem efficient in correcting this weakness, probably because employees in such form already participate in knowledge and learning activities in the context of their work and are ready for it. We also find that the interaction with the share of active LMP dedicated to start-up incentives is negative and significant. Compared with *Taylorism*, the negative effect of the *Independent* form of work organisation on vulnerability is larger in countries with higher expenditures on start-up incentives. Start-up incentives are programmes that promote entrepreneurship by encouraging the unemployment and

¹⁸ Taking the exponential of -0.867 and -1.309, we obtain that the odds of being vulnerable is 0.42 in Korea and 0.27 in Denmark while it is 0.44 in a country with zero expenditures on training (Slovakia, for example).

¹⁹ The same calculations show that the odds of being vulnerable are 0.44 in the UK while it is only 0.20 in Sweden.

target groups to start their own business or to become self-employed (OECD, 2014). Our results suggest that this policy also favours job stability in *Independent* organisations probably by enhancing the global entrepreneurship climate which contributes to the creation of sustainable start-ups.

There are no labour market policy and economic factors that amplify the negative effect of the *Simple* form of work organisation on the probability of being vulnerable. The % of active LMP as well as the share of passive LMP expenditures dedicated to out of income maintenance and support reduce the small protective effect of *Simple* form of work organisations compared with *Tayloristic* ones.

Finally, the degree of centralisation of wage bargaining, the strictness of employment legislation protection on the use of temporary contracts and the share of R&D expenditures in GDP are efficient in enhancing the protective effect of *Constrained Learning* organisations. On the contrary, the strictness of employment protection legislation in terms of individual and collective dismissals reduces its protective effect. These results stimulate reflexion about national policies that could encourage firms' organisational choices in order to adapt the forms of work organisation (especially *Discretionary Learning*) which protect individuals from vulnerability to non-employment.

[Table 6]

This analysis shows that employment policies need to take into account the structure of the economy in terms of forms of work organisations. Active labour market policies are efficient at protecting employment in countries where the *Discretionary Learning* and the *Independent* forms of work organisation are widespread. They are much less efficient in countries where *Taylorist* and *Simple* forms of work organisations are predominant. In such countries, economic growth is the best way of protecting employment. It is in countries where the *Constrained Learning* form of work organisation is the more widespread that the characteristics of the industrial relations system play a larger role in securing employment. Centralisation of wage bargaining and an employment protection legislation targeted on temporary contracts rather than regular employment favours the capacity of the *Constrained Learning* form of work organisation to secure employment.

6. Conclusions

Work organisation is often considered a central element in fostering economic and business development. In recent years, restructuring of organisations have been widely observed in many OECD countries. At the same time nonstandard work, as well as unemployment, has been on the rise. We argue that the capacity of workers to secure their employment in a changing work environment is related to the form of work organisation in which they are employed.

Most studies on labour market vulnerability rely on the study of supply side factors while the literature dealing with the concept of work organisation usually analyses it in terms of its relationship with productivity, innovation and working conditions rather than with labour market outcomes. This paper examines the relationship between the different forms of work organisation in workplaces and the vulnerability to non-employment within countries taking part in the Programme for the Assessment of Adults Competencies (PIAAC) – a cross-country survey carried out by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). Using hierarchical cluster analysis, we define five forms of work organisation based on the description given by employees of the tasks they perform: *Discretionary Learning*, *Constrained Learning*, *Independent*, *Simple* and *Taylorist*. Workers in *Discretionary Learning* have a higher degree of autonomy in the way they do their job, they plan their own activities and organise their own time on a daily basis. They are also more frequently involved in learning activities and in solving complex problems at work. The *Constrained Learning* form of work organisation differs from the *Discretionary Learning* in terms of discretion, problem solving and influence at work, but employees have more learning opportunities than in the other 3 forms of work organisation through collaborations and sharing of information as well as through on the job training. The *Independent* form of work organisation is below the overall mean for reading directions or instructions (less than once a week, but at least once a month) and on-the-job training. The *Simple* form of work organisation is opposite to the *Discretionary Learning* form as employees perform less frequently than in the average population all the listed tasks. Thus, they perform more simple jobs in more simple organisations. However, in this form of work organisation, compared to the *Independent* form, employees receive more on-the-job training. Finally, the Taylorist form of work organisation is characterised by below average frequency for all listed tasks except for two of them: cooperating or collaborating and sharing work-related information. The employees perform simple tasks in more structured organisations than in the *Simple* form.

Then multilevel logistic regression is used to evaluate their impact on vulnerability to non-employment. The latter is defined as being currently non-employed while having been employed at some point during the last twelve months previous the PIAAC survey. The results show indeed a significant impact of work organisation on vulnerability to non-employment after controlling for relevant job and personal

characteristics. However, its size depends on the type of work organisation. Compared to *Taylorism* all other forms of work organisation decrease the employees' probability of being vulnerable. In particular, employees in *Learning* forms work organisation, where they have a certain degree of discretion in the planning of their activities and time, are the least vulnerable.

An advantage of multilevel modelling is that it permits to analyse variables from different levels simultaneously, using a statistical model that properly organises these various dependencies. National factors, including labour market policies, business cycle or strictness of employment protection legislation could influence the probability of being vulnerable to non-employment. Our first results show that the protective effect of *Learning* forms of work organisation is particularly amplified by the share of expenditures on active LMP and their structure (% on training and % on employment incentives) while the share of out-of-income maintenance (i.e. passive LMP) reduces of the beneficial effects of this form of work organisation. The strictness of employment protection legislation regarding the use of temporary contract as well as the centralisation of wage bargaining enhance the protective effect of *Constrained Learning* form of work organisation.

Our results thus identify both the most protective forms of work organisation and the national policies which moderate their effect. They also show that employment policies need to take into account the structure of the economy in terms of forms of work organisations. Active labour market policies are efficient at protecting employment in countries where the *Discretionary Learning* and the *Independent* forms of work organisation are widespread. They are much less efficient in countries where *Taylorist* and *Simple* forms of work organisations are predominant. In such countries, economic growth is the best way of protecting employment. It is in countries where the *Constrained Learning* form of work organisation is the more widespread that the characteristics of the industrial relations system plays a larger role in securing employment. Centralisation of wage bargaining and an employment protection legislation targeted on temporary contracts rather than regular employment favours the capacity of the *Constrained Learning* form of work organisation to secure employment.

Finally, our results should stimulate reflections and further research on national policies that encourage firms' organisational choices in order to adapt the forms of work organisation (especially *Discretionary Learning*) which protect individuals from vulnerability to non-employment.

Table 1: Sample

Variable	Frequency	Weighted percentage
Adults who have had paid work during the last 12 months	117638	73.89
Adults who have not had paid work during the last 12 months	38208	24.31
Not known	1796	1.79
Total	157642	100
Eligible for Adult Education/Training population (AET)	106462	92.08
youths 16-24 in initial cycle of studies	11176	7.92
Total	117638	100
Employee	91895	85.44
Self-employed	13829	13.67
Not known	738	0.89
Total	106462	100
Employed	84330	90.97
Non-employed	7565	9.03
Total	91895	100
Could you tell me the main reason you stopped working		
Not known	52	1.75
I was dismissed	645	10.16
I was made redundant or took voluntary redundancy	1094	10.16
It was a temporary job which came to an end	2018	23.61
I resigned	495	5.44
I gave up work for health reasons	585	8.26
I took early retirement	335	3.09
I retired (at or after State Pension age)	474	6.05
I gave up work because of family responsibilities or child care	484	8.72
I gave up work in order to study	400	4.01
I left for some other reason	983	18.75
Total	7565	100
Non-vulnerable	84330	91.47
Vulnerable	7565-474=7091	8.53
Total	91421	100

Source: First round of the PIAAC survey by OECD (2012).

Figure 1: Vulnerability to non-employment and unemployment rate

Source: First round of the survey of adult skills (PIAAC, 2012) by OECD and OECD (2012), unemployment rate (indicator).

Coverage: These calculations include all countries that participated to the survey and take into consideration only those who have not worked a paid job during the last 12 months preceding the survey. It also do not take account of self-employed, youths 16-24 in initial cycle of studies (only Adult education/training population (AET)) and retired people.

Notes: These percentages have been computed using sample weights to adjust for many possible sources of biases. PIAAC unemployed is any person aged over 16 who is currently not employed, who has looked for a paid work at any time in the last 4 weeks, who has taken active steps to find a job and upon finding a job would have been able to start within 2 weeks or any person who will start a job within 3 months but is available to start a job within 2 weeks. OECD unemployed people are those who report that they are without work, that they are available for work and that they have taken active steps to find work in the last four weeks.

Table 2: Characteristics of the different forms of work organisation

	Discretionary learning	Constrained learning	Independent	Simple	Taylorism	Overall
	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean
Planning own activities	4.71	1.62	4.68	2.71	1.64	3.58
Organising own time	4.78	4.35	4.79	3.21	1.18	3.96
Solving complex problems	3.70	2.79	2.94	2.00	1.98	2.87
Sharing work-related information	4.69	4.67	4.59	1.74	4.61	4.23
Cooperating or collaborating	3.73	3.75	3.45	1.92	4.06	3.44
Persuading or influencing people	4.11	2.86	3.12	1.78	1.97	3.02
Read directions or instructions	4.22	3.68	3.23	2.22	2.76	3.36
On-the-job training	0.89	0.53	0.03	0.14	0.25	0.39
Overall	29.85	11.55	28.91	14.18	15.50	100

Source: First round of the survey of adult skills (PIAAC, 2012) by OECD.

Coverage: These calculations include all countries that participated to the survey and take into consideration only those who have not worked a paid job during the last 12 months preceding the survey. It also do not take account of self-employed, youths 16-24 in initial cycle of studies (only Adult education/training population (AET)) and retired people.

Notes: All variables except "on-the-job training" are rated based on how often skills are used as follows: 1 never, 2 less than once a month, 3 less than once a week but at least once a month, 4 at least once a week but not every day, 5 every day. The variable "on-the-job training" is a dummy variable indicating participation to job training. Therefore the line "On-th-job training" gives the share of each group involved in training activities at work. All these calculations use sample weights to adjust for many possible sources of biases. Bold figures means significantly greater than the overall value, otherwise significantly lower.

Figure 2: National differences in forms of work organisation

Source: First round of the survey of adult skills (PIAAC, 2012) by OECD.

Coverage: The calculations include all countries that participated to the survey and consider only those who have worked a paid job during the last 12 months preceding the survey. It also do not take account of self-employed, youths 16-24 in initial cycle of studies (only Adult education/training population (AET)) and retired people.

Note: These percentages have been computed using sample weights to adjust for many possible sources of biases.

Figure 3: Differences in forms of work organisation across industries

Source: First round of the survey of adult skills (PIAAC, 2012) by OECD

Coverage: These calculations include all countries that participated to the survey and take into consideration only those who have not worked a paid job during the last 12 months preceding the survey. It also do not take account of self-employed, youths 16-24 in initial cycle of studies (only Adult education/training population (AET)) and retired people.

Note: These percentages have been computed using sample weights to adjust for many possible sources of biases.

Figure 4: Differences in forms of work organisation across occupations

Source: First round of the survey of adult skills (PIAAC, 2012) by OECD

Coverage: These calculations include all countries that participated to the survey and take into consideration only those who have not worked a paid job during the last 12 months preceding the survey. It also do not take account of self-employed, youths 16-24 in initial cycle of studies (only Adult education/training population (AET)) and retired people.

Notes: These percentages have been computed using sample weights to adjust for many possible sources of biases.

Table 3: Forms of work organisation in OECD by vulnerability status

Work organisation	Overall (%)	Vulnerable (%)	Non-vulnerable (%)
Discretionary learning	29.85	15.48	31.23
Constrained learning	11.55	11.74	11.54
Independent	28.91	32.57	28.49
Simple	14.18	17.33	13.91
Taylorism	15.50	22.87	14.83
Total	100	100	100

Source: First round of the survey of adult skills (PIAAC, 2012) by OECD

Coverage: The calculations include all countries that participated to the survey and consider only those who have worked a paid job during the last 12 months preceding the survey. It also do not take account of self-employed, youths 16-24 in initial cycle of studies (only Adult education/training population (AET)) and retired people.

Note: These percentages have been computed using sample weights to adjust for many possible sources of biases.

Table 4: Country-level variables

Countries/ Variables	Labour Market Institutions										Economic factors		
	Expenditures on Labour Market policies (LMP)					Strictness of employment protection legislation		Centralisation of wage bargaining	% of services in employment	GDP growth in %	Expenditures in R&D in % of GDP		
	% of expenditures on active LMP	% on training	Active % on employment incentives	% on start-up incentives	Passive % out-of-income maintenance and support	Dismissal	Use of temporary contract						
Belgium	28	20	28	0	67	1.9	2.4	0.48	77	3.37	2.36		
Czech Republic	52	4	8	0	1	2.9	1.4	0.25	59	0.75	1.79		
Denmark	52	29	21	0	84	2.2	1.4	0.42	78	2.54	3.00		
Estonia	39	52	7	4	1	1.8	1.9	0.32	64	7.82	2.11		
Finland	42	50	15	1	95	2.2	1.6	0.43	73	0.94	3.42		
France	39	39	3	4	99	2.4	3.6	0.23	79	0.85	2.23		
Germany	41	33	4	4	95	2.7	1	0.47	70	1.85	2.87		
Ireland	27	44	8	0	99	1.4	0.6	0.46	76	2.11	1.56		
Italy	22	31	40	2	95	2.8	2	0.38	68	0.35	1.27		
Japan	44	5	45	0	1	1.4	0.9	0.32	70	3.87	3.34		
Korea	58	16	10	8	1	2.4	2.1	0.32	69	3.32	4.03		
Netherlands	35	11	3	0	1	2.8	0.9	0.57	80	0.50	1.94		
Norway	60	29	17	0	1	2.3	3	0.51	78	5.62	1.62		
Poland	57	2	21	12	66	2.2	1.8	0.17	57	4.79	0.88		
Slovakia	38	0	31	19	58	1.7	1.6	0.50	59	3.85	0.81		
Spain	17	23	27	17	99	2.2	2.7	0.38	75	0.84	1.28		
Sweden	67	8	50	1	1	2.6	0.8	0.52	78	2.41	3.28		
United Kingdom	42	4	4	0	1	1.3	0.4	0.11	79	3.44	1.62		

Source: OECD database and for the centralization measure, the database on institutional characteristics of trade unions, wage setting, state intervention and social pacts (ICTWSS) by Jelle Vesser. The total expenditures on LMP is in percentage of the GDP. The strictness of employment protection is based from an OECD index and range from 1 to 6 for each country. The measure of the centralisation of the wage bargaining takes into account of both union authority and union concentration at multiple level and range from 0 to 1.

Table 5: Fixed and random effects estimates

	Logistic regression		Multilevel logistic regression	
	Model 1	Model 2a	Model 2b	Model 3
Fixed Effects estimates				
Intercept	-1.429***	-1.554***	-1.929***	-1.929***
Work organisation (ref. Taylorism)				
Discretionary learning	-0.756***	-0.878***	-0.810***	-0.810***
Independent	-0.107	-0.095	-0.048	-0.047
Simple	-0.311***	-0.242***	-0.242***	-0.241***
Constrained learning	-0.253**	-0.297***	-0.302***	-0.302***
Random effects estimates				
Intercept	.	0.159 (0.053)	0.162 (0.054)	0.070 (0.023)
Discretionary learning	.	0.094 (0.031)	0.092 (0.031)	0.030 (0.010)
Independent	.	0.056 (0.018)	0.053 (0.018)	0.012 (0.004)
Simple	.	0.077 (0.026)	0.070 (0.023)	0.026 (0.009)
Constrained learning	.	0.176 (0.059)	0.148 (0.049)	0.040 (0.013)
Number of observations	68861	68861	66974	66974
-2 Log-likelihood	144004764	268297275	107412527	107412377

Notes: Singnificativity levels: *** 1%, ** 5%, * 10%. Standard errors are into parenthesis for the estimates of the random terms variances. All models control for personal (age, education, gender, marital status, family responsibilities and social and ethnic background) and job characteristics (sector of the economy, establishment size, industry, occupation, experience with ICT at work, type of employment contract and hours worked per week). Table A1 in the appendix shows estimates of coefficients attached to the control variables. In addition, Model 1 is a fixed effect model that control for countries. Model 2b and 3 are estimated removing individuals from Russia where country-level data are not available; Hence the different number of observations, but also keep in mind that sample weights are used. Model 2a and 2b are the same except Model 2b is estimated excluding Russia from the sample. Comparison of these two models enable to validate the use of a multilevel model. Model 3 considers country-level variables and their interactions with the forms of work organisation, and it enables to analyse differences between countries in the effect of work organisation. The lower number of observations (compared to the one in the descriptive tables and figures) results from the removal of Austria, Canada and United States from our initial sample (due to missing data). We also use sample weight in these estimations.

Table 6: Estimates for the coefficients attached to the country- and cross-levels interactions variables in Model 3

Country-level variable * Work organisation	Intercept	Forms of work organisation			
	Taylorism (reference)	Discretionary learning	Independent	Simple	Constrained learning
Labour Market Institutions					
Expenditures on labour Market policies (LMP)					
% on Active LMP	1.142*	-1.093**	-0.257	1.109***	0.178
Structure of expenditures on active LMP					
% on training	1.765***	-0.942**	-0.748***	-0.380	0.030
% on employment incentives	1.696***	-1.250***	-0.797***	-0.397	0.224
% on start-up incentives	3.282*	-1.381	-2.001**	1.160	1.219
Structure of expenditures on passive LMP					
% on Out-of-income maintenance and support	-0.335	0.789*	0.788***	0.813*	0.460
Strictness of employment protection legislation					
Individual and collective dismissals	-0.089	-0.090	-0.010	0.035	0.534***
Use of temporary contract	-0.079	-0.017	0.039	0.070	-0.172*
Trade union and wage setting					
Measure of the Centralisation of wage bargaining	-0.704	0.018	0.097	0.175	-1.972***
Economic factors					
Share of services in employment (%)	1.576	-0.427	-1.924***	0.246	1.068
GDP growth rate	-10.073*	0.444	1.740	3.167	1.456
Research & Development (% GDP)	-0.138	0.011	0.076*	-0.016	-0.208***

Note: Significant level at * 10%, **5%, ***1%. This table is not presenting the regression of the different forms of work organisation. It shows the estimates from the part of our random effect model with country level variables and their interactions with the different forms of work organisation. This way of presenting these results improve the readability. It clearly shows how differences between countries affect the relationship between work organisation and vulnerability to non-employment. The first column represents the direct effects of the country-level variables (estimates of the coefficients attached to them). It can also be considered the effect of the interaction with the form of work organisation of the reference individual (Taylorism). The other columns represent the estimates of the coefficients attached to the interaction between the country-level variables and the different forms of work organisation.

7. Appendix

Table A1: Job and sociodemographic characteristics by vulnerability status

Variables	Overall (%)	Vulnerable (%)	Non-vulnerable (%)
Characteristics of the employer			
Economic sector			
Private	71.3	74.1	71.1
Public	24.5	21.7	24.7
Nonprofit	4.0	3.4	4.1
Missing values	0.2	0.8	0.1
Establishment size			
<10 employees	23.4	33.1	22.5
11-50 employees	29.8	32.5	29.6
51-250 employees	23.7	19.0	24.2
251-1000 employees	12.9	7.8	13.3
>1000 employees	9.3	5.7	9.7
Missing values	0.8	1.8	0.7
Industry classification ISIC Rev 4			
A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing	1.4	2.6	1.3
BC: Manufacturing, mining and quarrying)	17.2	13.3	17.5
DE: Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply, and Water	1.7	2.6	1.6
F: construction	6.5	7.5	6.4
G: Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorc	12.8	15.0	12.6
H: Transportation and storage	5.7	4.6	5.8
I: Accommodation and food service activities	5.0	8.9	4.6
J: Information and communication	3.6	2.2	3.7
KL: Financial and insurance activities; Real estate activities	4.4	3.7	4.5
M: Professional, scientific and technical activities	4.3	5.6	4.2
N: Administrative and support service activities	4.5	6.8	4.3
O: Public administration and defence; compulsory social security	7.3	4.6	7.5
P: Education	8.7	7.1	8.8
Q: Human health and social work activities	12.3	9.9	12.5
R: Arts, entertainment and recreation	1.5	2.7	1.4
employers, undifferentiated goods- and services-producing activ.	2.7	2.3	2.7
Missing values	0.6	0.7	0.6

Source: First round of the survey of adult skills (PIAAC) by OECD.

Coverage: These calculations include all countries that participated to the survey and take into consideration only those who have not worked a paid job during the last 12 months preceding the survey. It also do not take account of self-employed, youths 16-24 in initial cycle of studies (only Adult education/training population (AET)) and retired people.

Note: In order to adjust for many possible sources of biases, these percentages have been computed using sample weights and their standard errors are estimated using jackknife method. Bold figures for one group means they have a significantly higher percentage.

Table A1: Job and sociodemographic characteristics by vulnerability status (continued)

Variables	Overall (%)	Vulnerable (%)	Non-vulnerable (%)
Characteristics of the job			
Occupational classification ISCO 1 digit			
0: Armed forces	0.6	0.4	0.6
1: Legislators, senior officials and managers	7.4	4.6	7.6
2: professionals	18.6	13.0	19.1
3: Technicians and associate professionals	15.4	9.8	15.9
4: Clerks	10.6	11.5	10.5
5: Service workers and shop and market sales workers	18.8	24.7	18.3
6: Skilled agricultural and fishery workers	0.9	1.5	0.8
7: Craft and related trades workers	10.6	11.0	10.5
8: Plant and machine operators and assemblers	8.6	8.2	8.6
9:Elementary occupations	8.1	14.5	7.6
Missing values	0.5	0.9	0.5
Type of employment contract			
Indefinite	49.4	30.4	51.1
Temporary	11.5	24.3	10.3
Others: temporary employment agency contract; apprenticeship o	6.9	14.1	6.2
Missing values (for Austria, United States and Canada)	32.2	31.2	32.3
Average number of hours worked per week (mean)	39.7	37.8	39.9
Experience with computer at work			
Use ICT at work	68.0	51.3	69.6
Do not use ICT at work	32.0	48.6	30.4
Missing values	0.0	0.1	0.0

Source: First round of the survey of adult skills (PIAAC) by OECD

Coverage: These calculations include all countries that participated to the survey and take into consideration only those who have not worked a paid job during the last 12 months preceding the survey. It also do not take account of self-employed, youths 16-24 in initial cycle of studies (only Adult education/training population (AET)) and retired people.

Note: In order to adjust for many possible sources of biases, these percentages have been computed using sample weights and their standard errors are estimated using jackknife method. Bold figures for one group means they have a significantly higher percentage.

Table A1: Job and sociodemographic characteristics by vulnerability status (continued)

Variables	Overall (%)	Vulnerable (%)	Non-vulnerable (%)
Sociodemographic characteristics			
Age in 10 year bands			
<24	6.5	13.0	5.9
25-34	26.2	30.3	25.8
35-44	26.2	21.7	26.6
45-54	25.4	19.6	25.9
55 plus	15.7	15.4	15.8
Education level			
Primary	2.8	5.3	2.6
Secondary	53.9	60.5	53.3
University	43.2	34.1	44.0
Missing values	0.1	0.1	0.1
Gender			
female	47.6	57.0	46.7
Male	51.6	42.4	52.4
Missing (for Austria)	0.8	0.6	0.9
Marital status			
Single	21.9	31.2	21.0
Living with spouse or partner	66.9	57.5	67.8
Missing values	11.2	11.3	11.2
Family responsibilities: Number of children			
No children	31.6	37.2	31.1
One child	19.9	19.8	19.9
Two children	30.9	23.0	31.6
Three children or more	17.6	20.0	17.4
Social background			
Immigration			
First generation immigrant	9.8	11.4	9.6
Second generation immigrant	2.6	3.4	2.5
Non 1st or 2nd generation immigrant	82.0	79.3	82.3
Missing values	5.6	5.9	5.6
Parents' level of education			
Uneducated parents	26.9	29.6	26.6
At least one educated parents	67.1	63.0	67.6
Missing values	6.0	7.4	5.8
Number of observations	91421	7091	84330

Coverage: These calculations include all countries that participated to the survey and take into consideration only those who have not worked a paid job during the last 12 months preceding the survey. It also do not take account of self-employed, youths 16-24 in initial cycle of studies (only Adult education/training population (AET)) and retired people.

Note: In order to adjust for many possible sources of biases, these percentages have been computed using sample weights and their standard errors are estimated using jackknife method. Bold figures for one group means they have a significantly higher percentage.

Table A2: (Multilevel) logistic regression estimates for coefficients attached to the control variables

	Logistic regression		Multilevel logistic regression	
	Model 1	Model 2a	Model 2b	Model 3
Fixed effects estimates				
Characteristics of the employer				
Economic sector (ref. private sector)				
public	0.090	0.096	-0.125	-0.125
Nonprofit	0.196	0.195	0.187	0.187
Missing values	0.662	0.716	0.599	0.599
Establishment size (ref. <10 employees)				
11-50 employees	-0.0834	-0.07998	-0.111*	-0.111*
51-250 employees	-0.300***	-0.298***	-0.201*	-0.201*
251-1000 employees	-0.451***	-0.450***	-0.324**	-0.324**
>1000 employees	-0.321***	-0.352***	-0.336**	-0.336**
Missing values	0.323*	0.315	-0.056	-0.056
Industry classification ISIC Rev 4 (ref. isic1_BC: Manufacturing, mining and quarrying)				
A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing	0.168	0.162	0.344**	0.344**
DE: Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply, ar	1.028***	1.030***	0.615***	0.615***
F: Construction	0.313***	0.299***	0.251*	0.251*
G: Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles ar	0.041	0.036	0.202	0.202
H: Transportation and storage	0.024	0.009	0.158	0.158
I: Accommodation and food service activities	0.337**	0.325***	0.401***	0.401***
J: Information and communication	-0.007	-0.024	0.290	0.290
KL: Financial and insurance activities; Real estate activiti	0.473***	0.471	0.773***	0.773***
M: Professional, scientific and technical activities	0.477**	0.467***	0.371***	0.371***
N: Administrative and support service activities	0.239*	0.225	0.361**	0.361**
O: Public administration and defence; compulsory social	-0.080	-0.107	0.236	0.236
P: Education	-0.051	-0.068	0.242*	0.242*
Q: Human health and social work activities	-0.057	-0.073	0.027	0.027
R: Arts, entertainment and recreation	0.420**	0.411*	0.585***	0.585***
STU: Other service activities; Activities of households as	-0.532***	-0.551***	-0.353**	-0.353**
Missing values	0.062	0.075	0.277	0.277
Characteristics of the job				
Occupational classification ISCO 1 digit (ref. ISCO 9 elementary occupations)				
0: Armed forces	0.032	0.033	-0.720	-0.720
1: Legislators, senior officials and managers	-0.187	-0.175	-0.614***	-0.614***
2: professionals	-0.158	-0.129	-0.270**	-0.270**
3: Technicians and associate professionals	-0.431***	-0.409***	-0.376**	-0.376**
4: Clerks	-0.043	-0.016	-0.123	-0.123
5: Service workers and shop and market sales workers	-0.142	-0.113	-0.106	-0.106
6: Skilled agricultural and fishery workers	0.042	0.048	-0.010	-0.010
7: Craft and related trades workers	-0.136	-0.119*	-0.089	-0.089
8: Plant and machine operators and assemblers	-0.204	-0.171**	-0.198**	-0.198**
Missing values	0.376	0.386*	0.331	0.331
Experience with computer at work (ref. Do not use ICT at work)				
Use of ICT at work	-0.348***	-0.355***	-0.383***	-0.383***
Missing values	0.413	0.424	-0.482	-0.482
Type of employment contract (ref. indefinite)				
Temporary	1.116***	1.126***	1.394***	1.394***
Others: temporary employment agency contract; appren	0.947***	0.952***	1.313***	1.313***
Missing values	0.819**	0.872***	0.901	0.901
Hours worked per week	-0.004	-0.004	-0.004	-0.004

Table A2: (Multilevel) logistic regression estimates for coefficients attached to the control variables (continued)

	Logistic regression		Multilevel logistic regression	
	Model 1	Model 2a	Model 2b	Model 3
Fixed effects estimates				
Socio-demographic characteristics				
Age in 10 year bands (ref. under 24)				
25-34	-0.255***	-0.262***	-0.152**	-0.152**
35-44	-0.436***	-0.442***	-0.346***	-0.346***
45-54	-0.572***	-0.569***	-0.475***	-0.475***
55 plus	-0.396***	-0.403*	-0.116	-0.116
Education level (ref. primary or less)				
Secondary	-0.4005***	-0.3689*	-0.2001*	-0.2001*
University	-0.4260**	-0.3868**	-0.2313*	-0.2313*
Missing values	-0.8220	-0.7872	-0.2841	-0.2841
Gender (ref. male)				
female	0.403***	0.399***	0.351***	0.351***
Marital status (ref. living with spouse or partner)				
Single	0.108	0.110	0.068	0.068
Missing values	0.178	0.180*	0.151	0.151
Family responsibilities: Number of children (ref. no children)				
One child	0.026	0.030	-0.045	-0.045
Two children	-0.186**	-0.1842*	-0.220	-0.220
Three children or more	-0.013	-0.019	-0.206	-0.206
Social background (ref. Non 1st or 2nd generation immigrant and Educated parents)				
First generation immigrant	0.209*	0.196	0.040	0.040
second generation immigrant	0.358	0.358*	0.202	0.202
Missing values	-0.121	-0.148	-0.171	-0.171
Uneducated parents				
Uneducated parents	-0.106	-0.106***	-0.106**	-0.106**
Missing values	-0.041	-0.043	0.027	0.027
Country (ref. France)				
Belgium	-0.633***	-	-	-
Czech Republic	-0.043	-	-	-
Denmark	0.317***	-	-	-
Estonia	-0.189**	-	-	-
Finland	0.136	-	-	-
Germany	-0.501***	-	-	-
Ireland	-0.172**	-	-	-
Italy	0.052	-	-	-
Japan	-0.151	-	-	-
Korea	-0.320**	-	-	-
Netherlands	-0.350***	-	-	-
Norway	-0.397***	-	-	-
Poland	-0.166*	-	-	-
Russia	0.299**	-	-	-
Slovakia	0.014	-	-	-
Spain	0.577***	-	-	-
Sweden	-0.003	-	-	-
United Kingdom	-0.173*	-	-	-
Number of observations	68861	68861	66974	66974
-2 Log-likelihood	144004764	268297275	107412527	107412377

Notes: This table shows estimates of the coefficients attached to the control variables as a complement to the results presented in Tables 5 and 6. Model 1 is a fixed effect logistic regression model that control for countries. Model 2b and 3 are estimated removing individuals from Russia where country-level data are not available. Hence the different number of observations; but also keep in mind that sample weights are used. Model 2a and 2b are the same except Model 2b is estimated excluding Russia from the sample. A comparison of these two models enables to validate the use of a multilevel model. Model 3 considers country-level variables and their interactions with the forms of work organisation, and it enables to analyse differences between countries in the effect of work organisation.

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InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion

Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

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